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MICRO FINANCE: AN EXTENSION OF BANKING SUPPORT TO UPLIFT POVERTY IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Microfinance is a type of banking service that is provided to unemployed or low-income individuals or groups who would otherwise have no other means of gaining financial services. The goal of microfinance is to give low income people an opportunity to become self-sufficient by providing a means of saving money, borrowing money and insurance. Microloans are given for a variety of purposes, frequently for microenterprise development. The diversity of products and services offered reflects the fact that the financial needs of individuals, households, and enterprises can change significantly over time, especially for those who live in poverty. Because of these varied needs, and because of the industry's focus on the poor, microfinance institutions often use non-traditional methodologies, such as group lending or other forms of collateral not employed by the formal financial sector.

The purpose of this research is to explore the effectiveness of Micro Finance to reduce poverty. This is the concern of this research whether Microfinance is being utilized properly by borrowers or it is not creating that much impact on major portion or people to get rid of poverty

Key words: Micro Finance, Credit, Poverty, Banking support

INTRODUCTION

Micro-finance is an innovative credit delivery mechanism to ensure viable financial services for the poor. It has the potential to address issues like actualizing equitable gains from the development on a sustained basis and can play a vital role in developing nations in fighting poverty.

Features of Microfinance:

1. The target customers of micro finance institutions are low income borrowers.
2. Amount of loan is comparatively low and it is provided for Short duration.

3. Loans are offered without collaterals
4. The main purpose of granting micro loan is generation of income for poor people.
5. Micro finance institutions provide other financial services like savings, insurance, remittance and non-financial services like individual counseling, training and support to start own business in a convenient way.
6. The borrower receives financial services at her/his door step and in most cases with a repayment schedule of borrower's convenience.
7. Interest rates charged by these institutions are higher than commercial banks and vary widely from 10 to 30 per cent.

In India microfinance operates through two channels:

1. SHG (Self Help Group) – Bank Linkage Programme (SBLP)
2. Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs)

SHG – Bank Linkage Programme (SBLP)

SHG – Bank Linkage Programme (SBLP) was initiated by NABARD in 1992. Under the SHG model the members in villages are encouraged to form groups of around 10-15. The members contribute their savings in the group periodically and from these savings small loans are provided to the members. In the later period these SHGs are provided with bank loans generally for income generation purpose. The group's members meet periodically when the new savings come in, recovery of past loans are made from the members and also new loans are disbursed. This model has been very much successful in the past and with time it is becoming more popular. The SHGs are self-sustaining and once the group becomes stable it starts working on its own with some support from NGOs.

Micro Finance Institutions

Micro finance institutions have microfinance as their main operation. A number of organizations with different size and legal forms offer microfinance services to the villagers. These institutions work on the concept of Joint Liability Group (JLG). A JLG is an informal group comprising of 5 to 10 individual members who come together for the purpose of availing bank loans either individually or through the group mechanism against a mutual guarantee.

Non-Banking Financial Companies (NBFCs), Co-operative societies, Section-25 companies, Societies and Trusts, all such institutions operating in microfinance sector constitute MFIs and together they account for about 42 percent of the microfinance sector in terms of loan portfolio. The MFI channel is dominated by NBFCs which cover more than 80 percent of the total loan portfolio through the MFI channel.

The reason for existence of separate institutions i.e. MFIs for offering microfinance are as follows:

- High transaction cost – generally micro credits fall below the break-even point of providing loans by banks
- Absence of collaterals – the poor usually are not in a state to offer collaterals to secure the credit
- Loans are generally taken for very short duration periods
- Higher frequency of repayment of instalments and higher rate of Default

Hierarchy of Financial Institutions for Microfinance Disbursement:-

S.No.	Type of MFI	Number	Legal Forms of MFIs	Legal registration
1	NGOs	400-500	Not for Profit	Social Registration Act, 1980, Indian Trust Act, 1882
2	Non-Profit Companies	20	Not for Profit	Section 25 of Indian Companies Act, 1956
3	Mutual Benefit MFIs, Mutual Aided Co-operative Societies	200-500	Mutual Benefit MFIs	Mutually Aided Co-operative Societies Act enacted by state government
4	Non-Banking Financial Companies	45	For Profit MFIs	Indian Companies Act, 1956, RBI Act, 1934

Literature Review

According to Dillinger (2003), Micro - Finance is broad range of service that indicates deposits, small loans, money transfer, payment services and various types of insurance products through the poor and low income household for their income generation and improving their living standards by investing micro enterprises and small business.

On the other hand according to (Mayoux, 2007), Micro - Finance is a stipulation of greater assortment of financial services for examples, small and medium loans, deposits, payment service, money transfer, insurance for the low income household as well as poor and their micro business. Especially microfinance service is provided from three different types of sources like rural banks and cooperatives as formal institutions, semiformal institutions like non-government organizations and informal source like shopkeepers as well as moneylenders.

Microfinance has got great influence on economic development of a country; some of the contributions are being discussed from the view point of several scholars:

Sundaresan (2008) mentioned that business starts with help of microfinance can also create jobs for other people along with entrepreneur himself. In some cases people create big investment from individual loan to start bigger business and whole community get benefit which creates employment for community people.

Financial Stability: One of the major roles microfinance is playing by providing financial stability to people which contributed to local economies in substantial extent. Arner (2007) argued that small loans have offered an opportunity to create extra income, so that people can pay for their extreme necessities. After availing financial aid through microfinance, people don't rely on any public assistance programs, which is indeed beneficial for the national economy.

Global Poverty: The supporters of microfinance believe that offering financial stability to poor and low income families through small loans may break the poverty cycle for future generations. As many of these communities started growing, the local economies are started flourishing. The gross domestic production of country started increasing and the gap between the poorest and wealthiest people has also decreased (Johnsong & Rugly, 2007).

Microfinance and poverty alleviation:

Microfinance plays an imperative function as an efficient tool to alleviation of poverty and encourages the productive exercise of poor people. It makes a great opportunity for employment by raising agricultural productivity through small farmers. It also creates enormous opportunities for self-employment (Ahmed, 2004).

According to Westover, (2008), Micro - Finance may help its borrowers to improve dignity as well as self confidence in conjunction with loan repayment with self-sufficiency that indicates sustainable income. Since Micro - Finance services initially focused on women, because it highlights that Micro - Finance leads to empower the women and help to break down gender inequalities by providing opportunities for women in order to participate in leadership roles as well as to fulfil the responsibilities.

Kabeer, quoted in Mosedale (2003, p.2) states that women need empowerment as they are constrained by “the norms, beliefs, customs and values through which societies differentiate between women and men”. She also states that empowerment refers to the “process by which those who have been denied the ability to make strategic life choices acquire such an ability”, where strategic choices are “critical for people to live the lives they want (such as choice of

livelihood, whether and who to marry, whether to have children, etc)” (Kabeer, 1999, p.437). Therefore MFIs cannot empower women directly but can help them through training and awareness-raising to challenge the existing norms, cultures and values which place them at a disadvantage in relation to men, and to help them have greater control over resources and their lives.

As highlighted, one of the key roles microfinance has to play in development is in bringing access to financial services to the poor, to those who are neglected by the formal banking sector. This is their social mission. Mainstream banks target clients that have collateral. The poor do not have assets to act as collateral, therefore they are ignored by the formal financial sector. These banks tend to be found in urban centres while the majority of the poor in the developing world live in rural areas, where financial services are not provided. Therefore, if MFIs are to fill this void they must reach the rural poor. However, according to most studies, microfinance is only reaching a small fraction of the estimated demand of the poor for financial services (Littlefield and Rosenberg, 2004). MFIs do not have the depth of outreach that is needed to meet the demands of the rural poor. Serving the rural poor in the developing world involves a major financial commitment, as it is expensive to run rural microfinance projects. Claessens (2005) states that high transaction costs, small volumes and the high costs of expanding outreach, make it unprofitable to serve the rural poor. It is for this reason that commercial banks are positioned in areas of high population density. However, if MFIs are to meet their social mission of serving the poor then financial services need to reach the rural poor.

MICRO-FINANCE BASED POVERTY ALLEVIATION PROGRAMMES

1. The Government of India (GOI) launched the Swarnjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana (SGSY) in 1999 where the major emphasis is on self-help group (SHG) formation, social mobilisation and economic activation through microcredit finance.
2. Up to March 2003, 13.38 lakhs groups were constituted in 33 States and Union Territories, of which 33,436 SHGs only could take up economic activities for their economic sustenance.
3. The Government provides assistance to the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) to take up activities such as group formation, micro-finance and economic activation.

4. The Rashtriya Mahila Kosh (RMK that is, National Credit Fund for Women) and the Department of Women and Child Development have their own programmes to provide micro finance for economic empowerment of the rural poor.
5. The year 2001-02 marked a decade of self-help group-bank linkage programme in India.
6. With the growing importance of the micro-credit through SHG-bank linkage in India, the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) in 1996 included financing to SHGs as a mainstream activity of banks under their priority sector lending.
7. It has been estimated that India has the world's largest micro-finance programme in terms of out-reach, with 7.8 million households accessing credit through 17,085 branches of the formal banking system under the micro-credit finance programme.

CURRENT POSITION OF MICROFINANCE IN INDIA

Microfinance seems to be failing to achieve its most noble goal: poverty alleviation. At worst, some lenders are contributing to a cycle of indebtedness and abuse, just like the loan sharks they sought to replace. Critics say the industry has grown too quickly for its own good, with too much rapaciousness and too little regulation. That has fostered a breakdown in lending discipline, with multiple loans to overextended borrowers, and allowed some unscrupulous players to thrive. Irresponsible lending leading to multiple loans without due diligence, unproductive loans for consumption and consumer durables, lack of transparency in operations, usurious interest rates, coercive recovery practices, have all resulted in hyper profits to microfinance institutions and impoverishment of the poor. Micro lenders, such as India's largest SKS Microfinance, give loans as low as \$20 to small business and farmers but have been accused of charging excessively high rates and using aggressive tactics to recover money from borrowers. India's government plans legislation to crack down on microfinance institutions to stop those charging exorbitant interest rates, a finance ministry official says. Legislation, sparked by a string of suicides by impoverished borrowers, is expected to come before lawmakers this year. India's southern state of Andhra Pradesh, where SKS Microfinance and many other major micro lenders are headquartered, passed legislation last year to cap lending rates and prevent strong-arm recovery practices. The most recent crisis to hit microfinance began in India's southern state of Andhra Pradesh, where allegations of widespread over-indebtedness, heavy-handed collection tactics and borrower suicides have stirred a national debate about regulating the industry. In October 2010, the state government

slapped restrictions on microfinance institutions that crippled lending and sent collection rates plummeting along with the share price of SKS Microfinance, India's largest for-profit micro lender. On January 19, 2011 the Malegam Committee Report, released by the Reserve Bank of India, recommended a range of new regulations for India's microfinance institutions, including interest rate caps, loan limits and income ceilings for borrowers.

CONCLUSION

In spite of various lacunas in the working of micro finance institutions, it has contributed to the reduction of poverty in rural poor. It has provided financial assistance to the poor in order to provide them economic and social independence. 2014 could be the year when Microfinance could re-emerge from the shadows and regain its rightful place in the world. Bandhan Financial Services has been given a banking license by RBI and it has announced that it will list the bank on stock exchange within the next 3 years. The excitement is so huge that when Bandhan Microfinance advertised for 15 posts , it received applications from 27,000 candidates .There are more than 50 large microfinance companies operating in India, and most of them have seen their business grow by 50-100% in the last financial year. In June 2014, CRISIL, a leading ratings agency released its list of top microfinance institutions in India. This comprehensive list is the most up to date overview of microfinance companies in India and lists the top 25 microfinance companies. Recently the government of India granted Self-Regulatory Organization (SRO) status to Microfinance Institutions Network (MFIN) which is the apex body of MFI's in India; this is considered a positive development and will benefit microfinance companies and clients in growing the entire sector.

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